

FEATURES OF WRITING COMPETENCE IN A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Annotation. In this article, the author analyzes the features of writing competence in a Foreign Language: linguistic, sociolinguistic, discursive and strategic skills. In this regard, he presents the definitions of the words "competence", "communicative competence", "written speech", "writing competence" given by foreign and national researchers. In turn, he explains the competence and its subcompetences.

Key words: component, skill, competence, written speech, writing competence, communicative competence.

Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada muallif chet tilida yozma nutq kompetensiyasi xususiyatlari: lingvistik, sotsiolingvistik, diskursiv va strategik kabi ko'nikmalar haqida so'z yuritgan. Bu borada "kompetensiya", "kommunikativ kompetensiya" "yozma nutq", "yozma nutq kompetensiyasi" so'zlariga xorij va milliy tadqiqotchilar tomonidan berilgan ta'riflarni taqdim etgan. O'z navbatida, kompetensiya va uning subkompetensiyalariga ham izoh bergan.

Kalit so'zlar: komponent, ko'nikma, kompetensiya, yozma nutq, yozma nutq kompetensiyasi, kommunikativ kompetensiya.

Аннотация. В данной статье автор анализирует особенности письменной компетенции на иностранном языке: лингвистические, социолингвистические, дискурсивные и стратегические. В связи с этим, автор приводит определения слов «компетенция», «коммуникативная компетенция», «письменная речь», «письменная компетенция» данные зарубежными и отечественными исследователями. В свою очередь, автор поясняет саму компетенцию и её субкомпетенции.

Ключевые слова: компонент, навык, компетенция, письменная речь, письменная компетенция, коммуникативная компетенция.

Written speech is essential in the process of teaching foreign languages. Through written speech, information is exchanged, stored, and it serves as an important tool in the formation of students' speech skills. The development of writing competence in English is pedagogically important, and this process requires the integration of students' linguistic knowledge, communicative skills, and cultural understanding. In this article, we are going to talk about the features of writing competence in a foreign language.

Foreign researchers such as M.A.K. Halliday, N. Nurfidah and A. Fandir, Bayatee Dueraman, I.G. Aynetdinova, N.M. Trubnikova, G.B. Rogova, A.A. Leontyev, O.V. Sitosanova, Uzbek researchers: J.J. Jalolov, S.U. Azizov, U.K. Khodzhanizayova, D. Israilova, D. Khusainova, R. Nazarov have discussed the issues about teaching writing in a foreign language. Before defining writing competence, we would like to explain the word "competence".

The CEFR describes competence as: "Knowledge and skills in a person that open the way for him to act." The CEFR divides competence into: 1) general (not specifically related to language, but applicable to all types of activity) and 2) communicative (allowing a person to use language tools). It is divided into linguistic, sociolinguistic and pragmatic subcompetences [1; p. 129]. Linguistic subcompetence, in turn, is divided into such

components such as lexical, grammatical, semantic, phonological, orthographic and orthoepic. [2; p. 52-55]. Pragmatic competence is the ability to use language correctly in various social situations. It includes the understanding and development of speech acts, politeness strategies, conversational rules and cultural norms.

Writing competence is the ability to express thoughts correctly, logically and grammatically in written form. Written speech consists of micro and macro texts that carry a communicative function. "Written speech is a form of expressing thoughts in writing, in text form" [3; p. 36].

Written communication skills consist of the following skills: (1) handwriting skills; (2) spelling skills; (3) composition skills; (4) lexical and grammatical skills of writing, etc. [4; p. 285]. The competence of written expression is characterized by a number of factors related to the speech situation, the intended purpose of communicative communication, the logicity of expressing thoughts, the use of lexical and grammatical means, and their compliance with language and speech norms. It is clear from this that the development of both competencies is carried out taking into account their psychological and linguistic characteristics. The componential features of written are the following: linguistic, sociolinguistic, discursive and strategic skills, which are tools which help develop written literacy in students.

Let us proceed to the explanation of the components of writing competence.

"Linguistic competence implies the acquisition of knowledge about language material (phonetics, lexis, grammar) and skills in speech activities (listening, speaking, reading and writing)" [1; p. 130].

"Sociolinguistic competence is the ability of a speaker to use a certain speech situation, communicative purpose and creates the opportunity to choose the necessary linguistic form, method of expression based on desire" [1; p. 136].

Discursive competence is the process of encoding (sending information) and decoding (receiving information) information by students studying a foreign language in accordance with the lexical, grammatical and syntactic norms of this language, in which they use the means of cohesion and coherence, taking into account style, genre, socio-cultural, psychological and emotional factors, to achieve a communicative goal" [5; p. 214].

"Strategic competence is the ability to use a sufficient repertoire of strategies based on the acquired knowledge and skills to achieve a communicative goal as effectively as possible" [6; p. 134]. Thus, strategic competence includes compensatory skills and abilities (the ability of students to overcome difficulties which arise in the communication process) and learning skills (the ability to independently use the acquired knowledge and correctly assess their own knowledge and the knowledge of other people).

In conclusion, the above-listed set of linguistic, sociolinguistic, discursive and strategic skills help students create logically coherent texts based on the content of paragraphs and correctly use syntactic structures.

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